

Entrepreneurship Skill Acquisition On Employability of Accounting Education Graduate Students in Rivers State Universities

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Abstract

This study investigated the Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition on Employability among Accounting Education Graduate Students in Universities in Rivers State. Three objectives, Three research questions and Three hypotheses formulated guided the study. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The population of this study was 140 accounting education students graduate from Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education. The entire population was used for the study hence there was no sampling. The instrument used for the study was "Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition on Employability among Accounting Education Graduate Students Questionnaire". The instrument was structured on a four-point rating scale of Very High Extent, High Extent, Low Extent and Very Low Extent. The instrument was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Business Education and one from Measurement and Evaluation Department all in the Faculty of Education. PPMCC was used for the reliability test which yielded reliability co-efficient of 0.78. Out of 140 copies of the questionnaire distributed only 135 copies was proper filled and retrieved which was used for the study. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, while T-test was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. It was revealed that Problem-Solving Skills give opportunity to utilize ones potentials. It was recommended among others that The University curriculum should seek to produce graduates that are critical and creative thinkers, with real skills, those who are ready to challenge the status quo, ready to make mistakes and learn from them. Graduates, who are not afraid to put forward novel ideas, listen to others and be ready to compromise where necessary. Entrepreneurship education in the universities should be adequately funded. This can be achieved through increase in the budgetary allocation to the universities by the government. With adequate funding, universities will be able to establish entrepreneurial development centers for practical work and the provision of training/instructional material for the programme.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Skill Acquisition, Employability, Accounting Education

INTRODUCTION

Education is the process of educating or being educated. It is also regarded as the theory and practice of teaching, or information about or training in a particular subject.. Accounting is one of the major occupational areas of vocational business education that can prepare the Nigerian workers and students for a job or employment within a wide range of business career such as payroll clerks, purchasing clerks, audit clerks, book-keepers, cashiers and business teachers who undertake the teaching of accounting to other learners. According to Ekpenyong (2015) accounting is the process by which data relating to the economics activities of an organisation are measured, recorded and communicated to interested parties for analysis and interpretation. He pointed out that accounting had its root on the need to keep the records of business transactions and that the chief reasons for keeping accounts are the need of the trader to know how much he owes, how much he owns, how much profit has been made and what his financial position is at a given time. Udo (2016) defined accounting as the process of identifying, measuring, and

communicating financial information to permit informed judgements and decisions by user of the information. He added that the role of accounting activities in the operation of business enterprises entails recording, classifying and summarising the enterprise monetary transactions and interpreting the results for both the internal and external end users of such information.

Entrepreneurship is a way of thinking, reasoning and acting that is opportunity based and holistic in approach. The term entrepreneur is synonymous with independent business activity. Different scholars have defined the term entrepreneur in a variety of ways. These scholars use different indices in defining the concept, owing to their different cultural, academic, environmental and social backgrounds. Osuala (2004) recognized entrepreneurs as those who possess a willingness to take risks while others stand to talk; identify opportunities to which others are blind and develop optimum confidence in themselves well beyond that of others. Nwachukwu (2010) viewed entrepreneurs as people, who have the

ability to see and evaluate business opportunities, gather the necessary resources to take advantage of them and initiate appropriate action to ensure success. To Nwachukwu, an entrepreneur is a risk taker, a man who braves uncertainty, strikes out his own and through devotion to duty and singleness of purpose somehow creates a business and industrial activity where none existed before. Entrepreneurship according to Akpomi (2012) stimulates and promotes economy, while entrepreneurs are innovators and job creators. Accordingly, Amesi (2011) viewed entrepreneurship as a mission for self-employment and success achievement through creativity, which is the hope of many Nigerians in entrepreneurship businesses. Entrepreneurship is the ability to create and build something from practically nothing. It has to do with doing, achieving, and building an enterprise or organization, rather than just watching, analyzing, or describing one. It refers to the willingness to take calculated risks, both personal and financial, and then do everything possible to get the odds in your favour (Wikipedia, 2018). Nzelum (2010) defined entrepreneurship education as a functional education and learning by doing. According to Kroom and Moolman (2019), entrepreneurship is described as the act of being an entrepreneur or undertaking innovations, finance in an effort to transform transactions into economic goods. This may result in new organizations or may be part of revitalizing mature organizations in response to perceived opportunities. Nwokolo (2012) viewed entrepreneurship as the totality of find and evaluate business opportunities, gather the necessary resources, initiate appropriate actions to ensure success. Entrepreneurship education is that aspect of education specifically designed to prepare the individual for the world of work in specific areas and to develop a level of maturity to be self-employed, to manage resources and create more wealth (Obasi, 2010).

Entrepreneurship is a process of bringing together creative and innovative ideas, combining them with management and organization skills in order to meet an identified need and thereby create wealth (Agomuo, 2012). It is the willingness and ability of an individual to seek out investment opportunities, establish and run an enterprise successfully. Entrepreneurship is thus, the process of learning the skills needed to assume the risk of establishing a business. Akpotowoh and Amahi (2016) opined that the skills acquired in any of the functional areas of business related programme promotes

training in entrepreneurship as well as equip Graduates with requisite potentials to establish and run small businesses on their own. According to Ademiluyi (2017), entrepreneurship skills are simply business skills which individuals acquire to enable them effectively function in the turbulent business environment as an entrepreneur or self-employed. Akinola (2011) pointed out that it takes special skills to succeed as an entrepreneur most especially the female folks. The future of the female entrepreneurs becomes worrisome due to gender-related discriminations prevalent in developing countries like Nigeria inclusive (Roomi & Parrot, 2018).

According to Andrea (2010) entrepreneurial skills ought to consist of five basic skills which include: human resource management skills, financial management skills, innovative skills, customer skills, marketing skills and management skills. Andrea opined that opportunities for employment as a result of Business Education preparation are enormous. These opportunities include development of small scale business, which if properly managed, will keep member of families gainfully employed and generate sufficient income with which to maintain their families and continually improve their standard of living. Olaleye (2010) identified technical skills as one of the entrepreneurial skills needed for self-employment. Obi (2015) stated that without graduates possessing enough technical skills in their various trades, other abilities cannot withstand the test of time. Obi affirmed that, if Business educator is to succeed in producing graduates who can gain and hold employment in a competitive world, it must endeavour to provide its graduates with adequate skills for entrepreneurship.

Skill acquisition is the ability to be trained on a particular task or function (Mike, 2014). Mike emphasized that the importance of skill acquisition includes self-employment, employment generation, effective function, and crime reduction. Idoko (2014) defined skill acquisition as the form of training by individuals or group of individuals that can lead to acquisition of knowledge for self-sustenance. It involves the training of people in different fields of trade under a legal agreement between the trainers and the trainees for certain duration and under certain conditions.

Ochiagha (2015) stated that skill acquisition is seen as the ability to do or perform an activity that is related to

some meaningful exercise, work or job. Ochiagha maintained that for skills to be acquired, appropriate knowledge, attitudes, habit of thought and qualities of character are learnt to enable the acquirer develop intellectual, emotional and moral character which prepares the individual for a brighter future. Similarly, Donli (2014) was of the view that skill acquisition is the manifestation of idea and knowledge through training which is geared towards instilling in individuals, the spirit of entrepreneurship needed for meaningful development. Donli (2014) further stressed that if individuals are given the opportunity to acquire relevant skills needed for self-sustainability in the economy, it will promote their charisma in any work or business situation.

According to Kazilan, Hamzah and Bakar (2019), employability refers to a group of important skills instilled in each individual in order to produce productive workforce. The concept of employability has in recent times remained the focus of government, employers, job seekers and educators. Brown and Hesketh (2014) defined employability as the relative chances of getting and maintaining different kinds of employment. While most people view employability in absolute terms, focusing on the need for individuals to obtain credentials, knowledge and social status; the concept of employability can also be seen as subjective and dependent on contextual factors. Employability not only depends on whether one is able to fulfill the requirements of specific jobs, but also on how one stands relative to others within a hierarchy of job seekers (Brown and Hesketh). Fugate et al (2014) defined employability as a form of an active adjustment of individuals towards certain occupations until they could identify and recognize existing career opportunities in the work place. It takes a skill for a job seeker to be able to identify opportunities where others could not identify. According to Kazilan et al (2009), employability refers to a group of important skills instilled in each individual in order to produce productive workforce. According to Hillage and Pollard (2008) as cited in Hind and Moss (2011), employability refers to a person's capability for gaining and maintaining employment. It is against this background that this study was designed to ascertain the Entrepreneurship Skills Acquisition on Employability among Accounting Education Graduate Students in Universities in Rivers State

Accounting is a systematic process of identifying, recording, measuring, classifying, verifying, summarizing, interpreting and communicating financial information to the users. It reveals profit or loss and income or expenditure for a given period; and the value and nature of a firm's assets, liabilities and owners' equity or the worth of a nation.

According to Asaolu (2019), Accounting is the process of recording, classifying, selecting, measuring, interpreting, summarizing and reporting financial data of an organization to the users for objective assessment and decision-making. The users of accounting information and records are students, management, government, employees, evaluators, creditors, financial analyst, the public, and so on. Accounting data is processed into accounting information through the use of accounting principles and conversions. Accounting principles are basic fundamental principles which guide in the preparation of the books of accounts and interpretation of financial statements. According to Udo (2018) accounting education is an area of study which is needed to equip the Nigerian workers and students with knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary for efficient financial calculation required for occupational competence and economic self-reliance. In agreement with the above, Udo (2012) stated that accounting education has a broad and comprehensive curriculum that provides every Nigerian worker and student with the help to acquire the basic and essential knowledge, skills, feelings, ideas, attitudes and understanding necessary to assume the roles of a worthy business man and as an effective and intelligent member of the Nigerian society. He added that accounting education leads to the development of better attitude to work because the individual knows that he/she is contributing to the growth of the society. Udo went on to say that accounting education is designed to develop skills encompassing knowledge and information needed by the Nigerian workers and students to enter and make progress in employment on a useful and productive basis. To him, accounting education is an integral part of the total education programme which contributes towards the development of good citizens by developing their physical, social, civic, cultural and economic competence. It also equips the recipients for a definite occupation and provides a basis for the vocational, technical and industrial know-how that makes the nation economically dependent.

Communication is a competence that can be regarded as the ability to interact appropriately and effectively with others (Chen & Starosta, 2016). Communication, which is a vital skill for all professions, is at the core of the teaching profession in terms of teacher-student relationships (Duță, 2015). The teaching profession requires perfect communication skills, because the potential of teachers to develop students is something related to effective communication. Thus, teachers should both communicate effectively with others and carry out technical tasks to be successful professionals (Ihmeideh, Al- Omari & Al-Dababneh, 2010).

Communication is indispensable to any organization's achievement. Communication is a critical point for human resource leaders which must be in alignment with the organization's management and its labour (Naresh, 2017). Communication involves at least two people: the sender and the receiver. There are four types of communication between senders and receivers: writing, speaking, listening, and conducting meetings. Each one is important to your success in the workplace. The four most common types of communication used by managers include interpersonal communication, nonverbal communication, written communication, and oral communication. Communication at its core is the transfer of information from one person to another with the information being understood by both parties. The central function of communication in an entrepreneurial setting is to reach a definite corporate goal. Communication in business conveys to the vital management functions which include planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling. The management process of decision making, coordinating, delegation, centralization and decentralization are all surrounded by communication.

Problem-solving is a crucial skill that affects all life actions, from simple to complex. It leads individuals to find solutions for the problems with the application of previously gained experiences (Korkut, 2012). Problem-solving skills support individuals' ability to cope with behaviour (Heppner, 2012). On the other hand, problem-solving, which is regarded as a challenging process, requires behavioural, affective and cognitive actions to overcome the barriers on the way to the goal (Jonassen, 2020). Individuals who have high levels of problem-solving skills tend to have a democratic attitude, show critical and reflective thinking (Demirel,

2014), and build effective communication (Payne, 2021). Problem-solving is a multifaceted process with behavioural, affective and cognitive dimensions, and which is essential in handling critical situations (Heppner & Lee, 2012). Hence, teachers' problem-solving skills should be developed, because teachers have to provide the best solution for issues that occur in every condition that they face in educational settings (Tok, Tok & Dolapçioğlu, 2014). It can also be asserted that teaching problem-solving to accounting education students could improve their skills on managing undesirable behaviors in the process of classroom setting. Problem-solving give students and teachers an opportunity to build an appropriate behavior in classroom settings with the help of effective communication (Emmer & Aussiker, 2010). Effective problem-solving skills help them to communicate and interact and understand their roles (Nelsen, 2020). Researches reveal that removing communication barriers has an effect on developing problem-solving skills (Ertürkler, 2019).

Statement of the Problem

Accounting is beneficial to both students, public and private office holders because it provides concepts, ideas, skills and knowledge for academic performance, financial information on any business for stakeholders and office holders, whether private or public. The knowledge of accounting exposes the learner to a number of skills that can be useful in nation building; and even in the conduct of one's personal life and own business.

However, the challenge is that graduates of higher institutions lack the competency to face the practical challenges in the labor market, and equally that graduates lack the employability skills. Most organizations today lament the lack of employable skills among Nigerian graduates, which mean that the organizations need to train and retrain graduates before they can be fully integrated into jobs. Employing and retraining them has been a problem due to financial involvement, equipment, tools, and the human element needed. Accounting Education Graduates students really need to be equipped, by acquiring both theoretical and practical entrepreneurship skills. Since the skills will make them effective and efficient in their area of specialization and will also enable them to have the mindset of becoming job creators instead of job seekers. Our present days organization stressed that many graduates do not have employable skills, which mean that the employer need to train and retrain them again before they can be fully absorbed into jobs. It is on this ground that this study sought to determine

entrepreneurial skills acquisition on employability of accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to determine the Entrepreneurship Skills acquisition on Employability of accounting Education graduate students in Universities in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. To determine the extent to which Problem-Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities
2. Ascertain the extent to which Information and Communication Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities
3. Ascertain the extent to which accounting skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study.

1. To what extent does Problem Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?
3. To what extent does Communication Skills improve accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?
4. To what extent does Accounting skills improve accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses that guided the study were tested at 0.05 levels of significance:

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of accounting education graduates in RSU and IAUE on the extent Problem Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities
- H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of respondents accounting

education graduate in RSU and IAUE on the extent Communication Skills improve accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

- H₀₃: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of accounting education graduate in RSU and IAUE on the extent Accounting skills improve accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

METHODOLOGY

This study was on entrepreneurship skill acquisition on employability of accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 140 accounting education graduate students. The entire population was used for the study. Three purpose of the study, three research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Entrepreneurship skill acquisition on employability of accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities”.

The instrument was structured on four point rating scale of Very High Extent (VHE) = 4, High Extent (HE) = 3, Low Extent (LE) = 2 and very Low Extent (VLE) = 1. Test-retest method was used to establish the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient was obtained 0.78. This shows that instrument was reliable. The copies of the instrument were administered to the respondent with the aid of the course representatives in the schools. Mean and standard deviation were used in analyzing the research questions while t-test was used in testing the hypotheses formulated in the study at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Research Question 1: To what extent do Problem Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Problem Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities(N = 135)

S/N	Items	RSU (60)			IAUE (75)		
		M	SD	RMK	M	SD	RMK
1	Ability to team up with experts in solving problems	3.30	0.66	HE	2.53	0.51	HE

2	Courage to take extreme measures to identified problem	3.17	0.63	HE	2.64	0.53	HE
3	Ability to implement a plan of action to resolve problem.	3.28	0.66	HE	2.67	0.53	HE
4	Problem-Solving Skills gives opportunity to utilize ones potentials.	3.27	0.65	HE	2.65	0.53	HE
5	Ability to believe that a solution exists for every problem	3.27	0.65	HE	2.77	0.55	HE
	Total Mean/SD	16.29	3.25		13.26	2.65	
	Grand mean/SD	3.26	0.65		2.65	0.53	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The analysis in table 1 shows that problem solving skills enhances the employability of accounting education graduate students in the following ways; ability to team up with experts in solving problems, courage to take extreme measures, implementation of plans and ability to believe that a solution exists for very problem.

Research Question 2: To what extent does Communication Skills improve accounting education graduate students in Universities in Rivers State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Information and Communication Skills improve accounting education graduate students in Universities in Rivers State

S/N	Items	RSU (60)			IAUE (75)		
		X	SD	RMK	X	SD	RMK
1	Ability to retrieve saved document	3.25	0.65	HE	3.76	0.55	HE
2	Ability to make business transaction on line	3.27	0.65	HE	2.60	0.52	HE
3	Independently operate personal computer systems	3.28	0.66	HE	2.99	0.59	HE
4	Perform data analysis with a computer package	3.27	0.65	HE	3.00	0.60	HE
5	Access and use information from the internet	16.44	3.28		14.02		
	Total Mean/SD	16.44	3.28		14.02	2.79	
	Grand mean/SD	3.29	0.66		2.80	0.56	

Source: Field survey, 2023

The analysis in table 2 shows that communication skill enhances the employability accounting education graduates in the following ways, ability to retrieve saved documents, make business transactions online, operate personal computer systems, perform data analysis and access and use information from the internet.

Research Question 3: To what extent do Accounting skills improve accounting education graduate students in Universities in Rivers State?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Accounting skills improve accounting education graduate students in Universities in Rivers State (N = 135)

S/N	Items	RSU (60)			IAUE (75)		
		M	SD	RMK	M	SD	RMK
1	Process accounts receivable and accounts payable	3.18	0.64	HE	2.73	0.55	HE

2	Process accounts receivable and accounts payable	3.27	0.65	HE	2.83	0.57	HE
3	Prepare final accounts, profit and loss accounts and the balance sheet	3.32	0.66	HE	2.75	0.55	HE
4	Prepare payroll and various deductions	3.30	0.66	HE	2.79	0.56	HE
5	Preparing daily cash reports as an accounting skill for economic survival	3.20	0.64	HE	3.04	0.61	HE
Total Mean/SD		16.27	3.25		14.14	2.84	
Grand mean/SD		3.25	0.65		2.83	0.57	

Source: Field survey, 2023

The analysis in table 3 shows that accounting skills improve accounting education graduate students in the following ways; process accounts receivable and payable, prepare final account, profit and loss accounts and balance sheet, prepare payroll and various deductions and preparing daily cash reports as an accounting skill for economic survival.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of RSU and IAUE accounting education graduate on the extent Problem Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4: t-test Analysis on the Mean Responses of RSU and IAUE accounting education graduate on the extent Problem Solving Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

Institutions	N	X	SD	DF	α	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
RSU	60	3.26	0.65	133	0.05	6.1	1.960	Rejected
IAUE	75	2.65	0.53					

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The analysis in table 4 shows that the t-cal (6.1) is higher than the t-crit (1.960). Hence the hypotheses was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE students on the extent to which problem solving, skills enhances employability of accounting education graduate student in Rivers State Universities.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of RSU and IAUE accounting education graduate on the extent communication Skills improve accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

Table 5: t-test Analysis on the Mean Responses of RSU and IAUE accounting education graduate on the extent communication Skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

Institutions	N	X	SD	DF	α	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
RSU	60	3.29	0.66	133	0.05	4.9	1.960	Rejected
IAUE	75	2.80	0.56					

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The analysis in table 5 shows that t-cal (4.9) is greater than the t-crit. (1.960). Hence, the hypotheses was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE students on the extent to

which communication skills enhances the employability of accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses 3: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of RSU and IAUE accounting education graduate on the extent Accounting skills improve accounting education graduate students in Rivers State Universities.

Table 6: t-test Analysis on the Mean Responses of RSU and IAUE accounting education graduate on the extent Accounting skills improve accounting Education graduate students in Rivers State Universities

Institutions	N	X	SD	DF	α	t-cal	t-crit	Decision
RSU	60	3.25	0.65	133	0.05	4.2	1.960	Rejected
IAUE	75	2.85	0.57					

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The analysis in table 6 shows that the t-cal (4.2) is higher than the t-crit (1.960). Hence, the hypotheses was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the mean responses of RSU and IAUE respondents on the extent to which accounting skill enhances employability of accounting education graduates' students in Rivers State Universities.

Discussion of Findings

Findings revealed that Problem-Solving Skills gives opportunity to utilize ones potentials. Courage to take extreme measures to identified problem and ability to implement a plan of action to resolve problem to a high extent. This finding is in agreement with the view of Reeve (2010) who opined that Problem-solving is a crucial skill that affects all life actions, from simple to complex. Problem-solving skills support individuals' ability to cope with behaviour. In agreement with the view of Funke, (2010) opined that problem-solving, which is regarded as a challenging process, requires behavioural, affective and cognitive actions to overcome the barriers on the way to the goal. Problem-solving is a multifaceted process with behavioural, affective and cognitive dimensions, and which is essential in handling critical situations and coping with problems.

Findings revealed that Communication Skills helps students Perform data analysis with a computer package and ability to retrieve saved document to a high extent. This finding is in agreement with the view of Abdulkarim (2012), who opined that Communication is the activity of conveying information through the exchange of thoughts, messages, or information, as by speech, visuals, signals, writing, or behavior. It is the meaningful exchange of information between two or more living creatures. The need for good communication skills, behaving appropriately in business situations and addressing situations in a professional manner are skills that businesses are looking for. In line with the view of Chen and Starosta, (2016) who opined that

communication is a competence that can be regarded as the ability to interact appropriately and effectively with others. Communication, which is a vital skill for all professions, is at the core of the teaching profession in terms of teacher-student relationships. The teaching profession requires perfect communication skills, because the potential of teachers to develop students is something related to effective communication. Thus, teachers should both communicate effectively with others and carry out technical tasks to be successful professionals.

CONCLUSION

Based on the data analysis in the study, findings and discussion made. The researchers concluded that Communication Skills helps students Perform data analysis with a computer package and Ability to retrieve saved document. It was concluded that Problem-Solving Skills gives opportunity to utilize one's potentials. Courage to take extreme measures to identified problem and Ability to implement a plan of action to resolve problem.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. The University curriculum should seek to produce graduates that are critical and creative thinkers, with real skills, those who are ready to challenge the status quo, ready to make mistakes and learn from them. Graduates, who are not afraid to put forward novel ideas, listen to others and be ready to compromise where necessary.
2. Entrepreneurship education in the universities should be adequately funded. This can be achieved through increase in the budgetary allocation to the

universities by the government. With adequate funding, universities will be able to establish entrepreneurial development centers for practical work and the provision of training/instructional material for the programme.

3. Government should provide relevant training facilities in all institutions for effective training of students

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